

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF CROP ROTATION FACTOR ON CROP YIELDS OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS IN POLISSYA OF UKRAINE

*Lysenko O.,
Derevianenko V.,
Kovalchuk M.,
Leskiv N.,
Humeniuk M.,
Adamitskyi B.,
Konovchuk V.,
Fedorchuk A.,
Moroz O.,
Didus S.,
Liushnenko A.*

*applicants for higher education Master's degree
Polissia National University
Zhytomyr, Ukraine*

ABSTRACT

The reform of the agricultural sector has led to a change in ownership and the formation of small farms with different economic capacities. As a result, these farms have changed the structure of their crop areas, crop rotations, and the overall level of agricultural technology and organisation, which has had a negative impact on the phytosanitary situation, reduced yields, and deteriorated product quality. Crop rotation is an essential factor for successful crop production. It has an impact on diseases and pests, the level of weeds and the supply of nutrients to all parts of the crop rotation. The most important source of nitrogen is the cultivation of legumes. On the one hand, it uses the ability of nodule bacteria to convert atmospheric nitrogen into nitrogen available to plants. Crop rotation has been shown to have a significant impact on crop productivity. The yield of winter wheat is 4.0 t/ha, spring wheat – 1.7 t/ha, winter rye – 3.2 t/ha, winter triticale – 3.7 t/ha, sowing millet – 1.5 t/ha, buckwheat – 1.1 t/ha, barley – 2.3 t/ha.

Keywords: inter wheat, spring wheat, winter rye, buckwheat, sowing millet, winter triticale, barley.

Problem statement. Ukraine is currently one of the largest exporters of grain crops to the global market. However, in order to maintain its leading position, it is necessary to steadily increase gross grain harvest.

Ukraine's grain industry is a strategic and most efficient sector of the national economy. Grain and products made from it have always been liquid, as they form the basis of the food supply and security of the state [1].

Unlike Western European countries, Ukraine has the capacity to develop and implement organic crop cultivation technologies on a large scale. A prerequisite for the development of biological crop production and the production of environmentally friendly products is that over the past 10–15 years, due to lack of funds, farmers have not used or used significantly lower rates of agrochemicals and pesticides. Whereas in Western Europe, up to 350 kg/ha of mineral fertilisers were applied at that time [2].

Climate change has posed many extremely important and challenging tasks for humanity, including the development and implementation of a strategy for its practical existence in such conditions. Based on numerous hydrometeorological indicators, domestic climate experts have concluded that a new climate has emerged in Ukraine over the past 10–25 years. Winters have become warmer and less snowy, and summers cooler. Sometimes there are sharp drops in air temperature – up to 10–12 °C per day. During such periods, atmospheric disturbances and natural phenomena, such

as heavy rains, thunderstorms, hail, wind, etc. usually occur [3].

An increase in global temperature of 2–3 °C causes permanent economic losses of 0–3 % of global production. With a warming of 5–6 °C, likely in the next century, the losses could reach 5–10 % of global GDP. The world is facing natural anomalies, so it is urgent to join forces to overcome the consequences of natural disasters and to address the challenges posed by global climate change. These changes pose a number of important challenges for Ukraine, including the development of an appropriate adaptation and mitigation policy [5].

Along with environmental friendliness, economy and profitability play a special role in the production of crop products in modern conditions. In Polissia, with its varied climatic conditions, many crops are not able to produce high and stable yields that would justify the costs of their production [1, 2].

In order to increase grain production and strengthen the livestock feed base, it is necessary to identify the place of grain crops in the structure of sown areas and field crop rotations. In order for crop rotation to fulfil its purpose, it is necessary to have an appropriate set of crops based on the soil and climatic characteristics of the zone, their optimal ratio in the structure of crops. The rational structure of crops allows for more efficient use of arable land and thus ensures the produc-

tion of more crop products and environmental protection. Field crops, depending on the amount of residual crop and root residues, have different effects on the processes of accumulation and mineralisation of soil humus [4].

The problem of preserving and improving soil fertility is closely linked to the use of all possible forms of organic fertilisers (manure, compost, green manure, straw, etc.). To ensure a deficit-free balance of humus in sod-podzolic soils, an additional 8.0 t/ha of good quality organic fertiliser is required, with the mandatory use of two-year grasses [6].

It is widely known that crop rotation is the basis of any zonal farming system, an important factor of intensification and creates conditions for the use of intensive technologies. The main task of crop rotation is to regulate the impact of cultivated plants on the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of the soil, water and temperature conditions.

One of the real ways to improve the situation in domestic agriculture is to incorporate traditional biological forms of soil fertility into crop rotation. Here, the greatest attention should be paid to expanding the practice of grass sowing and increasing the share of perennial grasses, especially legumes, in crop rotations.

The cultivation of legumes not only ensures the balance of protein in feed, but also replenishes the soil with biological nitrogen up to 300 kg/ha.

Thus, the crop rotation system still remains a key element of modern agriculture, as the whole range of tasks related to the rational use of arable land, restoration of soil fertility, its protection from erosion, environmental protection and the entire agricultural landscape can be solved only with an optimal ratio of crops within a scientifically sound and well-adapted crop rotation system for a given soil and climatic zone [5, 7].

Therefore, the aim was to study the influence of crop rotation on the growth and development of plants of the studied crops, which ensure the formation of high crop yields.

Research methodology. The field experiments were conducted during 2022–2023 in agricultural enterprises of different forms of ownership in Berdychiv and Zhytomyr districts of Zhytomyr region. The technology of growing crops in the experiment is generally accepted and recommended for the Polissya zone. The soil of the experimental plots is grey forest light loamy.

Meteorological conditions in 2022–2023 were characterised by uneven temperature and precipitation during the growing season.

In terms of hydrothermal conditions, 2022 was unstable and warm. The highest amount of precipitation was 162.5 mm in May, which was 279.5 % of the normal range. However, moisture deficits and an increase in average daily temperatures were observed in June, July and August, amounting to 4.0, 12.8 and 63.6 mm, respectively.

The weather conditions in June–August 2023 were characterised by instability: hot days were followed by cold ones, rainy periods by drought, and in the third decade of July, precipitation was 117 mm (303 % of the norm).

Weather conditions determine, first of all, the length of the growing season. The classic works of N. I. Vavilov (1957) state that the length of the growing season is determined by many properties of plants and varieties, which affect yields, product quality and the degree of exposure to adverse factors.

The study of the influence of crop rotation on crop productivity was carried out during 2018–2023 by conducting research in crop agrocenoses.

The following crop rotations were studied:

✧ three-seeded (perennial legumes – winter wheat – grain sorghum);

✧ four-crop (potatoes – winter rye – soya – buckwheat);

✧ five-field (perennial legumes – winter triticale – sowing millet – potatoes – spring barley).

In general, the weather conditions in 2022–2023 can be characterised as typical for Polissia, with temporary periods of no and low precipitation, high and low air temperatures, and low relative humidity during the growing season.

Hydrothermal coefficients (HTC) were significantly below the long-term average, with only the conditions in 2022 being close to the average. Thus, the weather conditions during the research constantly created abiotic stresses for plants, which allowed a comprehensive assessment of the productivity of all studied crops.

The statistical processing of the experimental data was carried out according to the generally accepted methodology using applied computer programs.

Research results. Negative trends are now developing: disruption of the frequency of crops in crop rotations and their abandonment, preference for business crops and displacement of legumes as fodder crops; formation of environmentally unfavourable agricultural landscapes with a reduction in natural elements; expansion of the use of agrochemicals; and increased environmental pressure on land and the environment. Global warming, caused by an increase in greenhouse gas emissions, has led to negative consequences in Ukraine: agricultural production does not even meet the needs of the domestic market; product quality does not always meet international standards; crop yields are much lower than in developed countries; and the constant growth of anthropogenic pressure on fertile soils exacerbates the problem of environmentally friendly farming [4].

Mass malnutrition and hunger are among the most important issues that are pushing the global community to the brink of extinction, and to varying degrees, this applies to both economically developed and developing countries. Insufficient food supply negatively affects people's life expectancy, health, physical performance, adaptation to modern high-tech production processes, etc.

Wheat is one of the oldest crops on the globe. Archaeological excavations and all literary data indicate that it was grown as early as 5–6 thousand years before Christ. It ranks first in the world among agricultural crops in terms of sown area. It originates from the Middle East or West Asia (Iraq, Egypt, China).

Wheat in a crop rotation spreads production costs, weather risks and agricultural operations across other crops. There are virtually no time requirements for the critical sowing period of corn and soybeans. The post-harvest period is ideal for applying lime, manure or mineral fertilisers. Farms specialising in maize production should recognise the benefits that wheat can provide.

Thus, the benefits of having wheat in the crop rotation include:

- ◇ improved soil quality;
- ◇ nutrient cycling;
- ◇ provision of nitrogen reserves;
- ◇ disruption of the cycle of annual and perennial weeds;
- ◇ protection of soil from erosion;
- ◇ distribution of agricultural operations;
- ◇ ensuring high profitability.

a

b

*Fig. 1 Agroecenosis of wheat
a) winter, b) spring*

Winter rye is one of the best predecessors for all crops. An important feature is its antagonism to other plants, including pink thistle, creeping wheatgrass, and bittergrass species. Enzymes contained in the root system of the crop are able to convert hard-to-reach forms of phosphorus and potassium into water-soluble compounds that can be absorbed by the root system of subsequent crops. This valuable function of rye is especially important in light, nitrogen-poor soils in crop rotation. Rye, as a precursor, provides significant yield

increases for such crops as potatoes, sugar beet, sunflower, rapeseed, corn, flax, etc.

The important role of rye in crop rotation in the fight against certain pathogens (for example, potato late blight, blackleg, *Alternaria*). When rye is used for green fodder (silage, haylage, hay), successful results have been achieved in growing sunflower, soybeans and corn as stubble crops in crop rotations in the central and western regions of Ukraine [4].

Fig. 2. Agroecenosis of winter rye

In terms of global production, millet is one of the top ten crops in the world. In Ukraine, production volumes of this cereal are declining significantly, although scientists say that millet can be profitable in the current

dry summer conditions. This is primarily due to the crop's peculiarities - the highest reproduction rate, high biological productivity potential even with strict self-pollination, drought resistance, salt tolerance, etc.

Fig. 3 Seed millet agrocnosis

Adherence to scientifically sound crop rotation. Millet is best planted on weed-free fields after winter crops, perennial grasses, legumes, and potatoes. It can be returned to its previous place in the crop rotation no earlier than after 3 years. Millet should not be sown after Sudanese grass, sorghum, chum, mung bean and maize, which are affected by many common pathogens and damaged by common types of pests. In areas of insufficient moisture, it should not be placed after crops that dry out the soil (sugar beet, sunflower) and reduce plant resistance to most diseases.

Millet is a crop that is demanding on its predecessors, as it grows slowly from germination to tillering and is suppressed by weeds. During this period, the activity of the root system is low, so fertile, weed-free fields should be allocated for millet sowing. The best predecessors are legumes, fertilised potatoes, sugar

beet, perennial grasses, melons, and in areas where there is no corn stem borer, corn. Poor predecessors for millet include millet, sorghum, sunflower, spring barley, and Sudanese grass.

Buckwheat is very important as a valuable cereal crop on a par with millet and rice. Buckwheat is a valuable food product with high taste and dietary qualities.

Buckwheat grain contains about 13 % protein, 67 % carbohydrates, 3 % oil, and 13 % fibre. Buckwheat protein consists mainly of easily soluble globulins and glutenins, which contributes to its better absorption (like legume proteins). Buckwheat contains a lot of amino acids and iron. The content of organic acids helps to assimilate not only buckwheat porridge, but also foods eaten after it. Buckwheat is a dietary product because it is rich in vitamins B1, B2, B5, etc.

Fig. 4 Buckwheat agrocnosis

Buckwheat is a good predecessor in crop rotation, as it reduces soil density and improves soil properties. It makes good use of the aftereffects of organic fertilisers applied to the previous crop. The best predecessors for buckwheat are potatoes, beetroot, and corn. Legumes, winter wheat, flax, and lupine are also good predecessors. The worst are spring cereals, sunflower, and sorghum.

Barley is currently one of the most common cereals in the world in general and in Ukraine in particular. Winter and spring barley are grown in our country. Given that it is not the right time to sow winter barley, let's talk about spring barley.

Fig. 5 Spring barley agrocnosis

Advantages of barley cultivation: the earliest maturing spring crop; one of the most widespread cereals in the world; the least demanding among cereals; high-yielding crop; good predecessor; available Ukrainian varieties are well adapted to local weather conditions; in arid areas, it is more productive than wheat.

In the structure of the farm's crop rotation, barley occupies a stable place – 5–6 % of the total area, i.e. 110–120 ha. Corn is considered to be the best precursor for spring barley here. And barley itself precedes sugar beet. The optimal time for sowing is the end of March.

Triticale is one of the crops with high soil fertility requirements. The best soils for it are chernozems, but it can also produce high yields on other soils with

proper agricultural practices. On light sandy and peaty soils, it produces higher yields than winter wheat because it tolerates soil acidity better. Triticale grain varieties have increased winter and drought resistance. The critical freezing point of the plants is 18–20 °C, while the critical freezing point of Myronivska 808 wheat is 17–18 °C. Plants are more resistant to ice crust and thaws, and grow back faster and better in spring than wheat. Increased drought tolerance is due to a well-developed root system. The protein content in triticale grain under the same growing conditions is 1–2 % higher than in winter wheat and 3–4 % higher than in winter rye.

Fig. 6 Agrocnosis of winter triticale

Triticale cereal varieties are placed in clean and busy pairs, as well as after peas. In Polissya regions, high grain yields of this crop can be obtained after early potato varieties. Satisfactory precursors are the layer and turnover of the perennial grass layer, silage corn harvested no later than two weeks before the optimal time for sowing winter crops, and poor precursors are cereal spiked crops. When sowing rye and wheat, their carrion clogs triticale crops, resulting in lower seed quality.

The productivity of agricultural crops, including the crops under study, is determined by a number of reasons. The volume and quality of the harvest depends on a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors: weather conditions, varietal characteristics of the crops grown, soil fertility, terrain features, the level of intensification of agricultural technologies, etc. As is well

known, changes in meteorological conditions alone can have a decisive impact on the yield and quality of crop production [3].

In the system of productive process management at the initial stages of plant growth and development, the moisture supply of crops, temperature regime and duration of the spring period with the sum of effective temperatures (above +10 °C) are crucial, which significantly affects their development. Temperature determines the rate of swelling, seed germination, duration of the sowing-germination period, as well as the timing of growth stages and the duration of interphase periods throughout the growing season [4].

Research has shown that the duration of the growing season in general and each individual phase of plant development directly depends on growing conditions,

moisture supply, air temperature, daylight hours and other factors.

One of the most important periods that significantly affects the level of plant productivity is the tube stage. During the years of research, this period lasted between 10 and 16 days. The longer this period is, the more plants have the opportunity to develop good vegetative mass. Favourable weather conditions during the flowering - milky ripeness period ensure the formation of a sufficient number of grains in the panicle for the formation of a future high yield. The duration of the interphase period was 20–24 days.

However, it should be noted that an increase in the duration of the milky-wax ripeness period leads to a decrease in yield. For example, excessive precipitation can cause an increase in the duration of this period, which leads to crop

losses and deterioration in quality. The yield level is also affected by elevated air temperatures, which result in shrivelled grain.

When designing and developing crop rotations, it is necessary to follow the rules for placing grain crops in descending order of value. In this regard, the placement of grain sorghum in three- and four-man rotations in the last link is justified. However, in a five-field crop rotation, a comparative approach to the placement of grain sorghum is determined by the expediency depending on the prevailing meteorological conditions or zonal characteristics.

During the years of research, the meteorological conditions of the growing season were quite dry, so the cultivation of drought-resistant and heat-resistant crops in Polissya is advisable to stabilise grain production. When assessing the grain yield of the studied crops, a fairly high average productivity was noted for 2022–2023.

Table 1

Crop yields in crop rotations, 2022-2023, t/ha

Culture	Yield, t/ha
Spring wheat	1,7
Winter wheat	4,0
Winter triticale	3,7
Winter rye	3,2
Spring barley	2,3
Proso millet	1,5
Buckwheat	1,1

The yields of the studied crops varied and changed over the years of research. Yields of winter wheat were 4.0 t/ha, spring wheat – 1.7 t/ha, winter rye – 3.2 t/ha, winter triticale – 3.7 t/ha, sowing millet – 1.5 t/ha, buckwheat – 1.1 t/ha, barley – 2.3 t/ha.

Conclusions. Thus, the crop rotation factor had a significant impact on the level of yield of the studied crops. Air temperature and precipitation had a significant impact on the formation, filling and ripening of crops. High air temperatures and lack of soil moisture shortened, while moderately warm and rainy weather extended, the period of grain ripening. Hot weather and moisture deficit in the one-metre soil layer accelerated this period by several days, while warm weather and sufficient moisture increased it. Thus, the development of the studied crops was also determined by the influence of abiotic factors during the growing season.

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